

Studies of Toxic and Heavy Metals Pollution of Karnafuli River and Its Impact on Public Health of Chittagong, Bangladesh

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to assess the toxic and heavy metals concentrations in water at different locations of the Karnafuli River. The assessment was carried out for various toxic and heavy metals concentrations in three seasons during pre-monsoon, monsoon and post-monsoon seasons for various continuous monitoring during the hydrological year 2014-2016. The statistical methods of sampling were used for collecting samples from different points of Karnafuli River. The samples were collected in high and low tide conditions. Since the water quality is expected to vary with season, multiple samples were collected at an interval of 2 to 3 weeks. The work has been carried out by traveling to the sampling sites for collection required water samples and the estimation of water discharge and determination of basic parameters of the sites. Samples were preserved with suitable preservation and transported to the laboratory. Standard methods were followed to determine the toxic and heavy metals concentrations. In the present study, seasonal variation hydro-chemical character of Karnafuli River water has been evaluated and assessed the suitability of water for human & animal's consumption, irrigation and industrial purposes. The study stress to access various essential heavy metals concentrations including arsenic, cadmium, cobalt, chromium, copper, iron, lead, manganese, nickel and zinc. Toxic and heavy metals concentrations were studied such as As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb, Mn, Ni and Zn were found in variation from (0.01 - 0.05)-mgL⁻¹, (0.12 - 0.75)-mgL⁻¹, (0.01 - 0.013)-mgL⁻¹, (0.051 - 0.063)-mgL⁻¹, (0.012 - 0.25)-mgL⁻¹, (0.006 - 4.844)-mgL⁻¹, (0.036 - 0.07)-mgL⁻¹, (0.015 - 0.845)-mgL⁻¹, (0.02 - 0.097)-mgL⁻¹, (0.013 - 0.8)-mgL⁻¹ respectively. The average of maximum heavy metals concentrations studied was found higher than

those of the World Health Organization (WHO), Department of Environment (DoE) and BSTI drinking water guidelines. The laboratory finding of water quality parameters were also compared with the recommended values set by DoE and BSTI. From Pearson correlation program, significant positive and negative correlations were found in different parameters. These assessment data indicated that the water quality of Karnafuli River are highly polluted which are continuously polluting the coastal zone, sea and the Halda river of Chittagong. The environmental impact of water quality of Karnafuli River has been discussed. A strategic water quality management plan has been proposed.

Keywords: Karnafuli River; toxic & heavy metals; pollution; tide variation; seasonal variation; environmental impacts; Chittagong; Bangladesh

Introduction

The Karnafuli is the principal river of Chittagong district of Bangladesh. It originates in the Lushai Hills of Mizoram of India, flows through Rangamati and the port city of Chittagong and discharges into the Bay of Bengal at latitude 22°12'N and longitude 91°47'E near Patenga. Water is a universal solvent an absolute necessity of life. It contains dissolved materials and suspended particles even in its natural state. Due to very good solvent property, it can dissolve toxic and hazardous substances and produce water pollution problems [1]. Water is one of the most important and abundant compounds of the ecosystem. All living organisms on the earth need water for their survival and growth. Earth is the only planet having about 70 % of water than other planets. But ,due to increased human population, industrialization, use of color dyes in textile industries , fertilizers in the agriculture and man-made activities affected the quality of water with different harmful contaminants especially textile effluents[2].Textile industry is one of the most important and rapidly developing industrial sectors in worldwide which consumes enormous amount of water as well as producers of wastewaters. The industrial pollution have affected not only the Corresponding surface water but also the soils and ground water even though industrial units have either constructed or connected to effluent treatment plants, the level of treatment has not been satisfactory at most of the places[3]. Water pollution is affecting the human lives of many people throughout the world as organic and inorganic pollution load in natural water is being increased. The implication of this is the pollution of surface water with consequent effects on human health. Effluents from industries had been known to contaminate water, soil and air with associated heavy disease burden and eventual shorter life expectancy in developing countries [4]. Various investigations indicate that most of the communicable diseases are water born and these diseases cause morbidity and mortality. Therefore, the mortality rate especially in the infants is very high in developing countries

like Bangladesh. The heavy metals levels up to μgL^{-1} levels in drinking water quality may cause saviors health problems and also cause cancer. In this study we made an attempt to know the concentration of eight heavy metals in ground water and surface water. These parameters are used to find out if the quality of water is good enough for drinking water, recreation, irrigation, and aquatic life. The general public of these countries is not well aware of water quality impacts on human health. Toxic metals in water and their effects: Cadmium, lead and mercury- Minamata disaster. Water born diseases: Cholera, dysentery and typhoid – Symptoms and medicines. Reduction in pollution or improvement in quality of water used for human consumption depends upon reliable analytical measurements [5-7]. Therefore, analytical water quality parameters are utmost important and are playing a key role for water pollution assessment. Examination of water quality (qualitatively and quantitatively) for the control and assessment of pollution is wide field in the present age. Aesthetic, physical, chemical including trace elements and bacteriological water quality parameters are the major groups. The amounts of wastewater are sharply increasing and the kinds of pollutants are also varied as the world wide industry is being developed incessantly. With respect to both the quantity and composition, the textile processing wastewater is recorded as the most polluted sources among all industrial sectors some metals are essential at low levels, serving as nutrients for animal and plant life but are toxic at higher level [8-10]. The sources of drinking water (both tap water and bottled water) include rivers, lakes, streams, ponds, reservoirs, springs and wells. As water travels over the surface of the land or through the ground, it dissolves naturally-occurring minerals and, in some cases, radioactive material, and can pick up substances resulting from the presence of animals or from human activity [11]. Some metals are essential at low levels, serving as nutrients for animal and plant life but are toxic at higher level. Arsenic is a carcinogen which causes many cancers including skin, lung, and bladder as well as cardiovascular disease. It was observed that dilution during rainy season decreases the metal concentration level to a considerable extent. The river acts as a source of drinking water, fishing and other domestic users for the inhabitants. Its watershed is subject to intensive human and industrial activities resulting in the discharge of a wide range of pollutants in most developing countries, control and monitoring of the quality of surface waters used for the production of drinking water are not systematic lack of means. From the scientific point of view, environmental monitoring campaigns produce large amounts of data that are often not easy to interpret [14-16]. Rapid industrialization and urbanization have caused contamination of the environment by heavy metals, and their rates of mobilization and transport in the environment have greatly accelerated since 1940s. Their natural sources in the environment include weathering of metal-containing rocks and volcanic eruptions, while principal anthropogenic sources include industrial emissions, mining, smelting, and agricultural activities like application of pesticides and phosphate fertilizers [17]. The effects of iron on aquatic animals and their habitats are mainly indirect, although the direct toxic effects of Fe^{2+} are also important in some lotic habitats receiving Fe-enriched effluents in cold seasons, in particular. Ferric hydroxide and Fe-

humus precipitates, on both biological and other surfaces, indirectly effect lotic organisms by disturbing the normal metabolism and osmoregulation, and by changing the structure and quality of benthic habitats and food resources [18]. Chromium is considered a serious environmental pollutant due to its wide industrial use. Contamination of soil and water by chromium (Cr) is of recent concern. Toxicity of Cr to plants depends on its valence state: Cr(VI) is highly toxic and mobile whereas Cr(III) is less toxic. Toxic effects of Cr on plant growth and development include alterations in the germination process as well as in the growth of roots, stems and leaves, which may affect total dry matter production and yield [19]. Cr is used widely in domestic and industrial products and that some of its chemical forms. North America all emphasize the high incidence of lung cancer and other respiratory diseases among workers involved in the manufacture of chromates [20]. It causes allergic and asthmatic reactions, is carcinogenic and is 1000 times as toxic as trivalent chromium. Health effects related to hexavalent chromium exposure include diarrhea, stomach and intestinal bleedings, cramps, and liver and kidney damage. Hexavalent chromium is mutagenic. Toxic effects may be passed on to children through the placenta. Metallic copper is malleable, ductile and a good thermal and electrical conductor. It has many commercial uses because of its versatility. Copper is found in surface water, groundwater, seawater and drinking-water, but it is primarily present in complexes or as particulate matter. Copper concentrations in surface water ranged from 0.0005 to 1 mgL⁻¹. The excess dose of copper can cause fatal hemolytic anemia and hepatic necrosis 0.01 to 1.7 mgL⁻¹ of copper in water has deleterious effect on health. It is more toxic in ionic form. It causes fatty metamorphosis of liver, necrosis of kidney [21]. Zinc has its primary effect on zinc-dependent enzymes that regulate RNA and DNA. The pancreas and bone are primary targets in birds and mammals; the gill epithelium is a primary target site in fish. Dietary zinc absorption is highly variable in animals; in general, it increases with low body weight and low zinc status and decreases with excess calcium or phytate and by deficiency of pyridoxine or tryptophan. The balance between excess and insufficient zinc is important. Zinc deficiency occurs in many species of plants and animals and has severe adverse effects on all stages of growth, development, reproduction, and survival. In humans, zinc deficiency is associated with delayed sexual maturation in adolescent males; poor growth in children; impaired growth of hair, skin, and bones; disrupted vitamin A metabolism; and abnormal taste acuity, hormone metabolism, and immune function [22]. The human beings activities may have significant adverse effects on the ecosystems health and the sustainability of resources. Heavy metals may occur in marine environment from natural practices and from discharges or leachates from a number of anthropogenic activities. The pollution of natural waters by heavy metals adversely affects marine biota and poses significant environmental risks and concerns. Monitoring programs and research on heavy metals in marine environment samples have become widely important due to concerns over accumulation and toxic effects in marine organisms and to humans through the food chain. Pollutants can persist for several years in marine sediments where they hold the possibility to affect human health and the environment

[23]. After industrial revolution and ever increasing urbanization, there has been a consistent addition of heavy metals in the environment, which is now becoming a challenge to produce from the contaminated soil. Industrial processing, mining, automobiles, use of synthetic fertilizers, and other agro-chemicals are building pools of various heavy metals of which lead, cadmium, arsenic, and mercury are of major concerns. Disease registry ranked lead as the second most harmful element due to its occurrence, toxicity, and exposure potential, after arsenic [24]. Iron is abundant in the earth's crust and occurs naturally in the aquatic environment; however, concentrations can be elevated due to human activities. Iron is a common pollutant in waters near coal and hard rock mine disturbances [25]. Iron is present in many water supplies. Iron is rarely present in water at concentrations greater than 10 mgL^{-1} however concentrations as low as 0.3 mgL^{-1} are enough to stain drinking water a reddish brown color and cause many issues for the homeowner. Manganese is the twelfth most abundant metal in the earth's crust and occurs in over 300 different minerals. Which places it next to iron in the periodic table of the elements; a feature of great practical significance in water treatment. Nearly all iron ores and even purified iron compounds contain manganese as a "contaminant", a fact that cannot be overlooked in plants in which iron flocculation is employed. Manganese is an essential element occurring in a very large number of plants, and a prominent United States Food and Nutrition Board recommends an "adequate" adult intake of approximately 2mg per day [26]. Nickel is a very abundant natural element. It occurs in earth's crust at 80 mgL^{-1} and in sea water at 2-5 μgL^{-1} . The human body contains about 10 mg Ni, about 18% in skin and rest in tissues. Nickel is found in all soil and is emitted from volcanoes. Nickel is also found in meteorites and on the ocean floor. These persons breathed amounts of nickel much higher than levels found normally in the environment. Workers who drank water containing high amounts of nickel had stomach ache and suffered adverse effects to their blood and kidneys [27]. The Karnafuli, a major river of Bangladesh, is polluted in several ways particularly through industrial and sewage disposal [28]. People of Chittagong city depend on Karnafuli for variety of aspects. Numerous industries are the major source of water pollution. The important industries in Bangladesh include tanneries, garments, ship breaking, pulp and paper, refineries, food, fertilizer, textile, pharmaceuticals, steel, chemical and other small-scale and agro-based industries. Increased anthropogenic activities have increased the potential pollution of the river, especially, the toxic and heavy metal pollutants. Rashed et al. [32] reported that the availability of the toxic and heavy metal in river water directly affects the fish physiology and by the consumption ultimately affects the human health. Hence, regular monitoring of pollution levels in the river is indispensable.

Fig. 1. Stranded boats and black water at the Karnafuli River (Source: The Daily Star).\

Fig. 2. Wastes floating in the Karnafuli River at Chanrdoghona at Paper Mill area.

Fig. 3. Stranded boats on Chaktai Canal

Sampling Areas

Our present work focused on the water quality status of stagnant and open river water resources in the Karnafuli River of the Greater Chittagong district [1]. Pollution sources are due to discharge of domestic and industrial effluents are shown in **Fig 1-3**. A total number of 100 water quality monitoring stations were identified (**Fig.-4**) and water samples were collected in the middle month of three seasons namely pre monsoon (January-March), monsoon (July-September), and post monsoon (October-December) of the hydrological years 2014-2016 for continuous monitoring of water quality parameters. Water samples from different points or spots of Karnafuli River region were collected for this study. A brief discussion of study area of Karnafuli River is given in **Fig.-4**.

Surface samples from different points of Karnafuli River Chittagong districts were collected for this study. Samples were collected in amber color polyethylene bottle cleaned by rinsing thoroughly with 8M HNO₃, followed by repeated washing with distilled water. Multiple samples were collected from the same spot in different seasons to study the seasonal variation of the results. The surface water samples were collected in the boat if possible in the middle of the flow. Two to four equal volumes were collected from vertical section. The water samples were collected within 3-18 inches from the surface of the water. Surface water Samples were collected using acid-leached polythene bottles (1-mLL⁻¹ HNO₃) and chilled immediately to 3° to 4°C. The samples were mixed well and a sample of 1.0-1.5 L was transferred for analysis in the laboratory [28, 29]. The analysis of water parameters is the basis of water quality monitoring. The analytical techniques commonly used are summarized in below [30, 31].

Preliminary treatment of samples for heavy metal determination

Preliminary treatments of samples were done by following international standard method given by APHA [30]. Water Sample was agitated to obtain homogeneous suspension of solids. 500-mL sample was measured and transferred to an evaporating dish; sample was acidified with 5 ml HNO₃ and evaporated on a steam bath to 15 to 20 ml. Then the solution was transferred, together with any solids remaining in the dish, to a 125-mL conical flask. 5 ml additional HNO₃, 5-mL H₂SO₄ and few glass beads (to prevent bumping) were added into the solution and it was evaporated on a hot plate until dense fumes of SO₃ appear in the flask. A clear solution was observed and all the HNO₃ was removed. The solution was cooled to room temperature and neutralized with NH₄OH then carefully diluted to about 50-mL and filtered through a Whatman No. 4 filter paper & washed the residue with 2 small portion of water. Then the filtrate was transferred quantitatively to a 100-mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark with de-ionized water. A aliquots of this solution were taken for the determination of metals

Fig. 4. Map showing the Sample Collection points of Karnafuli River

Analytical techniques

The samples were analyzed by a Shimadzu (Kyoto, Japan) (Model: AA7000) atomic absorption spectrophotometer equipped with a microcomputer-controlled air acetylene flame. An automated hydride generation - atomic absorption spectrophotometer, Type: iCE 3300 AA system, Thermo Scientific, designed in UK was used to determine arsenic. A Shimadzu (Kyoto, Japan) (Model: -1800) double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer was used for all the spectroscopic measurements of the standard metal solutions as well as the sample solutions were done at their respective wavelength of maximum absorptions λ_{\max} using a concurrently prepared calibration graph.

Table 1. The following analytical methods were used for determination of toxic and heavy metals.

Toxic and heavy metals	Analytical Techniques
Cadmium	FAAS
Chromium	FAAS
Copper	FAAS
Cobalt	FAAS
Iron	FAAS&Spectrophotometry
Lead	FAAS
Manganese	FAAS
Nickel	FAAS
As	AHG-AAS &Spectrophotometry
Zinc	AAS

FAAS: Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry

AHG-AAS: Automated Hydride Generation - Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer

Results

Karnafuli River water resources quality are shown in **Table(1.1-1.10)**, Karnafuli River water quality at different tide conditions, Karnafuli River water quality at different seasons, comparative study with WHO, BSTI, and also inter country rivers and the results of Pearson Correlations among the different parameters of Karnafuli River are shown in **Table 2, 3,4 and 5**, respectively.

Table 1. 1. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Sikolbaha Canal to Anumajhir Ghat

Parameters	Units	1. Sikolbaha canal	2. Raja khali Canal	3. Chakti canal	4. Fisharighat Canal	5. Jalilgang canal	6. Bangobari canal	7. Firingibazar canal	8. Karnophulighat	9. Majhirghat	10. Anumajhirghat
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.005	BDL	0.014	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.004	0.025	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	BDL	0.13	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.012	0.016
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.06	0.011	0.026	0.031	0.021	0.015	0.011	BDL	0.04	0.013
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.055	0.06	0.055	0.053	BDL	BDL	0.054	BDL	BDL	0.054
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.056	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.075	0.096	0.096	0.098	0.096
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.038	0.047	0.041	0.058	0.052	0.045	0.029	0.031	0.036	0.029
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.953	1.86	1.34	2.03	0.96	1.28	0.75	0.50	0.40	0.98
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.023	0.021	0.022	0.025	0.021	0.020	0.021	0.023	0.024
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.012	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.04	0.013

Table 1. 2. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Banglabazaar Ghat to Power point.

Parameters	Units	11. Banglabazarghat	12. Sadorghat	13. Current centre	14. Boal khali Kalago	15. Boalkhali Teksho canal	16. Boal khali Kalago canal	17. Ajgajja para	18. Ship Yard	19. Western Marine Ship Yard	20. Power point
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	0.02	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.01	BDL	BDL	0.01
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.024	BDL	0.004	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.004	BDL	0.004	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.015	0.013	BDL	0.012	0.015
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	0.054	BDL	0.053	BDL	0.055	BDL	0.052	0.058	BDL	0.057
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	0.011	0.021	0.012	0.023	BDL	0.025	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.014
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.01	0.01	0.21	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.25	0.26	0.26
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.49	0.62	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.07	0.11	0.08	0.12
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.025	BDL	0.023	BDL	0.027	BDL	0.024	BDL	0.026	BDL
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.014

Table 1.3. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Under Karnafuli Bridge to JT No. 1.

Parameters	Units	21. Under Karnaphulli bridge	22. East Mastuhara	23. West Mastuhara	24. Under Tower of mastuhara	25. North side bridge	26. New chaktai	27. Boalkhaikolago village(East)	28. Boalkhali village (West)	29. Talmarighat	30. JT No. 1
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.02	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.03	0.02	BDL	BDL
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.014	BDL	0.003	BDL	0.003	0.015	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.021
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.014	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.015	BDL	BDL	0.012
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.013	0.011	0.015	0.016	BDL	0.014	0.012	0.015	BDL
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.052	BDL	0.053	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.054
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.24	0.23	0.26	0.23	0.22	0.24	0.38	0.32	0.31	0.32
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.07	0.044	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.064	0.10	0.11	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.15	0.20	0.10	0.07
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.021	BDL	0.024	0.021	BDL	0.024	BDL	0.023	0.024	BDL
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.013	0.018	BDL	BDL	0.015

Table 1. 4. Karnafuli River water resources quality from JT No. 2 to JT No. 10.

Parameters	Units	31. JT No. 2	32. JT No. 3	33. Janarcanal	34. JT No. 4	35. JT No. 5	36. JT No. 6	37. JT No. 7	38. JT No. 8	39. JT No. 9	40. JT No. 10
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.04	0.03	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.04	BDL	BDL	0.04
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.013	0.014	0.008	BDL	BDL	0.023	BDL	0.021	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.013	0.013	0.012	0.011	0.015	0.014	0.016	0.017	0.012	0.014
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.015	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.015	0.021	0.023	0.025
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	0.061	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.054	BDL	0.057	0.052	0.051	BDL
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	3.13	1.63	2.76	3.24	4.32	4.84	3.37	3.34	3.47	3.26
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.054	0.042	0.068	0.038	0.037	0.04	0.04	0.308	0.056	0.038
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.64	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.11
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.21	0.023	0.024	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.023	0.024	0.021	BDL
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.019	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.021	0.023	BDL

Table 1.5. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Super Petrochemical to Dhanar canal North.

Parameters	Units	41. Super Petrochemical	42. Super Petrochemical (North)	44. BNK Nirvik	43. Star Cement	45. Star Cement (North)	46. Khatghor North	47. Khatghor	48. Star Cement (East)	49. Canal in between Star Cement	50. Dhanar canal North
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.05	0.04	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	BDL	0.04	BDL	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.025	BDL	0.023	0.021	0.043	BDL	BDL	0.010	0.004	0.01
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	BDL	BDL	0.015	0.015	BDL	BDL	0.13	BDL	0.01
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.018	0.017	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.016	BDL
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	0.054	0.052	0.053	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.055	BDL	0.052	BDL
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	3.21	4.02	3.64	3.86	2.94	3.76	2.86	2.64	2.48	3.11
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.041	0.0402	0.04
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.08	0.15	0.20	0.03	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.11	0.94
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.022	0.24	BDL	BDL	0.026	0.032	BDL	0.025	0.02
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.024	0.021	0.023	BDL	BDL	0.025	0.023	0.024	BDL	0.02

Table 1. 6. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Dhanar canal to Aminpara.

Parameters	Units	51. Dhanar canal	52. In between Dhanar canal and Diamond factory	53. Diamond factory	54. S. Alam refined sugar (North)	55. S. Alam refined sugar	56. Coastguar	57. Coastguar(North)	58. Moilarchor	59. Polyhard	60. Aminpara
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.02	0.01	BDL	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.02
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.016	BDL	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.14	BDL	BDL	0.16	0.18
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.13	BDL	0.014
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.012	0.011	0.012	0.015
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.053	0.052	BDL	0.053	BDL	0.061	0.060
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	3.00	.124	2.86	2.64	2.98	2.54	3.84	3.45	BDL	BDL
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.04	0.045	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	BDL	0.04
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.06	0.069	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.04
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.021	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.003	0.002
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.24	0.035	BDL	0.21	0.026	0.012	0.086	0.26	0.26	0.21

Table 1.7. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Jeleparakahl to Choudhury Para.

Parameters	Units	61. Jeleparakhal	62. Ispahani	63. Kalurghat (South)	64. Kalurghat breeze	65. Kalurghat (North)	66. Ramurhat (South para)	67. Ramurhat (middle para)	68. Bagrar canal	69. Roujan canal	70. Choudhurypara
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.01	0.02	BDL
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.75	0.64	0.24	0.51	0.42	0.56	0.52	0.12	0.13	0.12
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	BDL	0.017	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.018	BDL
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	0.014	0.15	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.25	0.23	0.22	0.025	0.023
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	0.0652	0.052	BDL	0.054	BDL	0.058	BDL	0.051	BDL	0.063
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.34	0.36	0.8	0.44	0.46	0.11	0.21	0.23	0.48	0.045
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.021	0.022	BDL	BDL	0.018	0.015	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.013
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.02	0.25	0.08	0.12	0.11	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.23
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.012	0.009	0.007	0.016	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.02
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.23	0.22	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.5

Table 1. 8. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Amurhat (South Para) to Choudhuryhat Koutoli.

Parameters	Units	71. Amurhat (South para)	72. Amurhat (North para)	73. Amurhat (West para)	74. Fakirakhali (North)	75. Fakirakhali (middle para)	76. Fakirakhali(South para)	77. Boalkhali (Sourth)	78. Boalkhali (middle para)	79. Boalkhali (North)	80. ChoudhuryhatKoutoli
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.02	0.01	0.02	BDL	BDL	0.02	0.03	0.01	BDL
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.22	0.29	0.07	0.06	0.05	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.013	0.014	0.012	0.016	BDL	0.016	BDL	BDL	0.012	BDL
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	0.008	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.012	0.013	0.012	0.02	0.021	0.023
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.051	BDL	BDL	0.052	0.053	0.052	BDL
Iron	Mg L ⁻¹	0.12	0.18	0.16	0.21	0.19	0.15	0.07	0.14	0.18	0.19
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.017	BDL	0.021	0.023	0.035	BDL	0.024
Manganese	Mg L ⁻¹	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.11
Nickel	Mg L ⁻¹	0.035	0.032	0.023	0.047	0.05	0.03	0.003	0.008	0.003	0.006
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.8	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.10	0.02	0.21

Table 1. 9. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Koutoli (South) to Kumara Chor (North).

Parameters	Units	81. koutoli (South)	82. Kajibari (North)	83. Kajibari (South)	84.kalurghat (East)	85. Water supplier	86. Soyabin factory	87. Soyabin factory (South)	88. Kumirarchor(South)	89. KumirarChor	90. KumirarChor(North)
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.04	0.03	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.04	BDL	0.05	BDL	0.03
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.04	0.27	0.26	0.27	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.05
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.013	0.012	0.011	0.014	0.014	0.012	BDL	BDL	0.016	BDL
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	0.066	0.06	0.052	0.032	0.026	0.006	0.005	0.021	0.20	0.018
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	BDL	0.05	BDL	0.053	0.051	BDL	BDL	0.054	0.054	0.053
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.51	0.48	0.81	0.75	0.65	0.16	0.17	0.582	0.45	0.09
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.017	0.015	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.15	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.12	0.11	0.03	0.047	0.04
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.004	0.026	0.002	0.007	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.005
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.023	0.022

Table 1. 10. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Karnafuli Paper Mill to Meshing hat and Airport to Navy gait.

Parameters	Units	91. Karnafuli Paper Mill	92. 250m South of Karnafuli Paper Mill	93. Kola bagan	94. 400m South from Karnafuli	95. 250m Karnafuli Paper Mill from	96. Meshinghat	97. Air port	98. Merine Academy	99. KAFCO	100. Navygait
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	BDL	0.02	0.03	0.01	BDL	0.01	0.01	BDL	0.02
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.023	0.026	BDL	0.025	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.014	0.012	0.015	0.014
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.015	0.017	0.024	0.023	0.011	0.003	0.025	0.021	0.024
Chromium	mg L ⁻¹	0.052	0.052	0.053	0.056	0.061	0.062	0.062	0.052	0.051	0.052
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.1	0.12	0.07	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.16	0.15	0.18	0.11
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	0.023	0.021	BDL	0.024	0.21	0.011	BDL	0.015	0.053	0.12
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05
Nickel	mg L ⁻¹	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.022	0.011	0.003	0.012	0.021
Zinc	mg L ⁻¹	0.24	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02

Table 2. 1. Karnafuli River water quality resources from Sikol Baha Canal to Anumajhir Ghat at different conditions.

Parameters	Units	Conditions	11. Banglabazar Ghat	12. Sador Ghat	13. Current centre	14. Boal khali Kalago	15. Boalkhali Teksho Canal	16. Boal khali Kalago	17. Ajgajja para	18. Ship Yard	19. Western Marine Ship Yard	20. Power point
As	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.017	0.017	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.009	BDL	BDL	0.009
		High tide	0.02	0.02	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.01	BDL	BDL	0.01
Cd	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.021	BDL	0.003	BDL	0.019	BDL	0.003	BDL	0.003	BDL
		High tide	0.024	BDL	0.004	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.004	BDL	0.004	BDL
Co	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.009	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.013	0.011	BDL	0.011	0.013
		High tide	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.015	0.013	BDL	0.012	0.015
Cu	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.048	BDL	0.047	BDL	0.049	BDL	0.046	0.051	BDL	0.051
		High tide	0.054	BDL	0.053	BDL	0.055	BDL	0.052	0.058	BDL	0.057
Cr	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.009	0.019	0.011	0.020	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.019	BDL	0.012
		High tide	0.011	0.021	0.012	0.023	BDL	0.025	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.014
Fe	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.008	0.009	0.186	0.213	0.213	0.213	0.213	0.222	0.231	0.231
		High tide	0.01	0.01	0.21	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.25	0.26	0.26
Pb	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.035	0.044	0.044	0.035	0.053	0.035	0.044
		High tide	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.05
Mn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.43	0.551	0.062	0.071	0.097	0.0711	0.062	0.097	0.071	0.106
		High tide	0.49	0.62	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.07	0.11	0.08	0.12
Ni	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.022	BDL	0.020	BDL	0.024	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.023	BDL
		High tide	0.025	BDL	0.023	BDL	0.027	BDL	0.024	BDL	0.026	BDL
Zn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.012
		High tide	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.014

Table 2. 2. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Banglabazaar Ghat to Power point at different conditions

Parameters	Units	Condition	1. Sikolbaha canal	2. Raja khali canal	3. Chakti canal	4. Fisharighat Canal	5. Jaijigang canal	6. Bangobari canal	7. Firingbazar canal	8. Karnophulighat	9. Majhirghat	10. Anumajhirghat
As	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.02	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.01	0.02	BDL
		High tide	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL
Cd	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.004	BDL	0.013	0.022	BDL	BDL	0.004	0.02	BDL
		High tide	BDL	0.005	BDL	0.014	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.004	0.025	BDL
Co	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.011	BDL	0.117	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.011	0.014
		High tide	0.012	BDL	0.13	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.012	0.016
Cu	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.054	0.01	0.023	0.03	0.019	0.013	0.01	BDL	0.036	0.012
		High tide	0.06	0.011	0.026	0.031	0.021	0.015	0.011	BDL	0.04	0.013
Cr	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.05	0.054	0.049	0.048	BDL	BDL	0.049	BDL	BDL	0.049
		High tide	0.055	0.06	0.055	0.053	BDL	BDL	0.054	BDL	BDL	0.054
Fe	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.050	0.063	0.081	0.054	0.072	0.067	0.086	0.086	0.088	0.08
		High tide	0.056	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.075	0.096	0.096	0.098	0.096
Pb	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.0504	0.063	0.081	0.054	0.072	0.067	0.086	0.086	0.088	0.086
		High tide	0.038	0.047	0.041	0.058	0.052	0.045	0.029	0.031	0.036	0.029
Mn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.8577	1.674	1.206	1.827	0.864	1.152	0.675	0.45	0.36	0.882
		High tide	0.953	1.86	1.34	2.03	0.96	1.28	0.75	0.50	0.40	0.98
Ni	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.021	0.019	0.02	0.022	0.019	0.018	0.019	0.021	0.022
		High tide	BDL	0.023	0.021	0.022	0.025	0.021	0.020	0.021	0.023	0.024
Zn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.011	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.011	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.036	0.012
		High tide	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.012	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.04	0.013

Table 2. 3. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Under Karnafuli Bridge to JT No. 1 at different conditions.

Parameters	Units	Condition s	21. Under Karnaphulli Bridge	22. East Mastuhara	23. West Mastuhara	24. Under Tower of mastuhara	25. North side bridge	26. New chaktai	27. Boalkhalikol agovillage(E)	28. Boalkhali village (Mooet)	29. Talmari Ghat	30. JT No. 1
As	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.02	0.01	0.01	BDL	0.01	BDL	0.02	0.01	BDL	BDL
		High tide	0.03	0.02	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.03	0.02	BDL	BDL
Cd	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.012	BDL	0.002	BDL	0.002	0.013	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.018
		High tide	0.014	BDL	0.003	BDL	0.003	0.015	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.021
Co	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.012	0.011	BDL	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.011
		High tide	0.014	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.015	BDL	BDL	0.012
Cu	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.011	0.009	0.013	0.014	BDL	0.012	0.011	0.013	BDL
		High tide	BDL	0.013	0.011	0.015	0.016	BDL	0.014	0.012	0.015	BDL
Cr	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.045	BDL	0.046	BDL	0.049	BDL	0.049	BDL	0.047
		High tide	BDL	0.052	BDL	0.053	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.054
Fe	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.21	0.201	0.227	0.201	0.192	0.21	0.332	0.28	0.271	0.28
		High tide	0.24	0.23	0.26	0.23	0.22	0.24	0.38	0.32	0.31	0.32
Pb	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.061	0.038	0.035	0.043	0.035	0.035	0.035	0.044	0.044	0.043
		High tide	0.07	0.044	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.056	0.087	0.096	0.043	0.035	0.035	0.131	0.175	0.087	0.061
		High tide	0.064	0.1	0.11	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.15	0.2	0.1	0.07
Ni	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.018	BDL	0.021	0.018	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.020	0.021	BDL
		High tide	0.021	BDL	0.024	0.021	BDL	0.024	BDL	0.023	0.024	BDL
Zn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.011	0.015	BDL	BDL	0.013
		High tide	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.013	0.018	BDL	BDL	0.015

Table 2. 4. Karnafuli River water resources quality from JT No. 2to JT No. 10 at differentconditions

Parameters	Units	Conditions	31. JT No. 2	32. JT No. 3	33. Janar Canal	34. JT No. 4	35. JT No. 5	36. JT No. 6	37. JT No. 7	38. JT No. 8	39. JT No. 9	40. JT No. 10
As	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.0342	0.0257	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.034	BDL	BDL	0.034
		High tide	0.04	0.03	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.04	BDL	BDL	0.04
Cd	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.011	0.012	0.006	BDL	BDL	0.019	BDL	0.018	BDL
		High tide	BDL	0.013	0.014	0.008	BDL	BDL	0.023	BDL	0.021	BDL
Co	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.011	0.011	0.0102	0.009	0.012	0.012	0.013	0.014	0.010	0.012
		High tide	0.013	0.013	0.012	0.011	0.015	0.014	0.016	0.017	0.012	0.014
Cu	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.013	0.0102	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.013	0.018	0.019	0.021
		High tide	BDL	0.015	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.015	0.021	0.023	0.025
Cr	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.052	BDL	0.048	BDL	0.046	BDL	0.048	0.044	0.043	BDL
		High tide	0.061	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.054	BDL	0.057	0.052	0.051	BDL
Fe	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	2.682	1.397	2.365	2.777	3.702	4.148	2.888	2.862	2.974	2.794
		High tide	3.13	1.63	2.76	3.24	4.32	4.84	3.37	3.34	3.47	3.26
Pb	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.0462	0.036	0.058	0.032	0.031	0.034	0.034	0.264	0.048	0.032
		High tide	0.054	0.042	0.068	0.038	0.037	0.04	0.04	0.308	0.056	0.038
Mn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.548	0.06	0.068	0.094	0.094	0.094	0.077	0.068	0.077	0.094
		High tide	0.64	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.11
Ni	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.18	0.019	0.020	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.019	0.020	0.018	BDL
		High tide	0.21	0.023	0.024	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.023	0.024	0.021	BDL
Zn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.010	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.018	0.019	BDL
		High tide	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.019	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.021	0.023	BDL

Table 2. 5. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Super Petrochemical to Dhanar Canal North at different conditions.

Parameters	Units	Conditions	41. Super Petrochemi	42. Super Petrochemi cal (North)	43. Star Cement	44. BNK Nirvik	45. Star Cement (North)	46. Khat Ghor North	47. Khat Ghor	48. Star Cement (East)	49. Canal in between Star	50. Dhanar Canal North
As	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.04	0.03	BDL	BDL	0.02	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.04
		High tide	0.05	0.04	BDL	BDL	0.03	BDL	BDL	0.04	BDL	0.05
Cd	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.023	BDL	0.019	0.020	0.039	BDL	BDL	0.009	0.004	0.009
		High tide	0.025	BDL	0.021	0.023	0.043	BDL	BDL	0.01	0.004	0.01
Co	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.011	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.118	BDL	0.009
		High tide	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.015	BDL	BDL	0.13	BDL	0.01
Cu	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.015	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.014	BDL
		High tide	BDL	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.017	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.016	BDL
Cr	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.049	0.047	BDL	0.048	BDL	BDL	0.05	BDL	0.047	BDL
		High tide	0.054	0.052	BDL	0.053	BDL	BDL	0.055	BDL	0.052	BDL
Fe	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	2.918	3.654	3.509	3.309	2.672	3.418	2.6	2.4	2.254	2.827
		High tide	3.21	4.02	3.86	3.64	2.94	3.76	2.86	2.64	2.48	3.11
Pb	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.036	0.045	0.036	0.036	0.036	0.036	0.036	0.037	0.036	0.036
		High tide	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.041	0.040
Mn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.036	0.072	0.181	0.136	0.027	0.063	0.072	0.018	0.1	0.854
		High tide	0.04	0.08	0.2	0.15	0.03	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.11	0.94
Ni	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.218	BDL	0.023	0.029	BDL	0.022	0.018
		High tide	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.24	BDL	0.026	0.032	BDL	0.025	0.02
Zn	mgL ⁻¹	Low tide	0.021	0.019	BDL	0.020	BDL	0.022	0.020	0.022	BDL	0.018
		High tide	0.024	0.021	BDL	0.023	BDL	0.025	0.023	0.024	BDL	0.02

Table 3. 6. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Dhanar Canal to Aminpara at different seasons (continued).

Parameters	Units	Seasons	51. Dhanar Canal	52. In between Dhanar Canal and Diamond	53. Diamond factory	54. S.Alam refined sugar	55. S.Alam refined sugar	56. Coast guar	57. Coastguar(Nor th)	58. Mollarchor	59. Polyhard	60. Aminpara
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.018	0.009	BDL	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.027	BDL	0.018
		POM	BDL	0.02	0.01	BDL	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.02
		Monsoon	BDL	0.022	0.011	BDL	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.033	BDL	0.02
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.021	BDL	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.186	BDL	BDL	0.213	0.24
		POM	0.016	BDL	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.14	BDL	BDL	0.16	0.18
		Monsoon	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.126	BDL	BDL	0.144	0.162
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.143	BDL	0.015
		POM	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.13	BDL	0.014
		Monsoon	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.113	BDL	0.012
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.062	BDL	0.058	0.057	BDL	0.058	BDL	0.067	0.066
		POM	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.053	0.052	BDL	0.053	BDL	0.061	0.06
		Monsoon	BDL	0.049	BDL	0.046	0.045	BDL	0.046	BDL	0.053	0.052
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	3	0.124	2.86	2.64	2.98	2.54	3.84	3.45	BDL	BDL
		POM	3.75	0.155	3.575	3.3	3.725	3.175	4.8	4.312	BDL	BDL
		Monsoon	2.7	0.111	2.574	2.376	2.682	2.286	3.456	3.105	BDL	BDL
Iron	mgL ⁻¹	Winter	0.069	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.07	0.1	0.1	0.04	0.04
		Summer	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.003	0.002	0.053
		Monsoon	0.0552	0.056	0.064	0.072	0.048	0.056	0.08	0.08	0.032	0.032
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.24	0.035	BDL	0.21	0.026	0.012	0.086	0.26	0.26	0.21
		POM	0.32	0.046	BDL	0.28	0.034	0.016	0.114	0.346	0.346	0.28
		Monsoon	0.192	0.028	BDL	0.168	0.0208	0.0096	0.0688	0.208	0.208	0.168
Manganese	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.048	0.055	0.056	0.064	0.072	0.048	0.056	0.08	0.08	0.032
		POM	0.06	0.069	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.07	0.1	0.1	0.04
		Monsoon	0.055	0.060	0.061	0.07	0.078	0.052	0.061	0.087	0.087	0.035
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.016	BDL	0.02	0.019	BDL	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.002	0.002
		POM	0.021	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.003	0.002
		Monsoon	0.018	BDL	0.021	0.021	BDL	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.002	0.002
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.192	0.028	BDL	0.168	0.020	0.009	0.068	0.208	0.208	0.168
		POM	0.24	0.035	BDL	0.21	0.026	0.012	0.086	0.26	0.26	0.21
		Monsoon	0.21	0.031	BDL	0.183	0.022	0.010	0.075	0.227	0.227	0.184

Table 3.7. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Jejeprakhhal to Choudhury Para at different seasons.

Parameters	Units	Seasons	61. Jejeprakhhal	62. Ispahani	63. Kalurghat (South)	64. Kalurghat Breeze	65. Kalurghat (North)	66. Ramurhat (South para)	67. Ramurhat (middle para)	68. Bagrar Canal	69. Roujan Canal	70. Choudhurypar
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.01	0.01	BDL	0.01	BDL	0.01	BDL	0.01	0.01	BDL
		POM	0.02	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.01	0.02	BDL
		Monsoon	0.02	0.01	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.01	0.02	BDL
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	1	0.653	0.32	0.68	0.56	0.646	0.611	0.16	0.173	16
		POM	0.75	0.64	0.24	0.51	0.42	0.56	0.52	0.12	0.13	12
		Monsoon	0.675	0.576	0.216	0.459	0.378	0.504	0.468	0.108	0.117	10.8
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.013	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.016	BDL	0.019	BDL
		POM	0.012	BDL	0.017	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.018	BDL
		Monsoon	0.010	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.010	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.015	BDL
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.058	0.046	BDL	0.048	BDL	0.0522	BDL	0.045	BDL	0.056
		POM	0.065	0.052	BDL	0.054	BDL	0.058	BDL	0.051	BDL	0.063
		Monsoon	0.072	0.057	BDL	0.06	BDL	0.064	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.07
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.021	0.022	BDL	BDL	0.018	0.015	BDL	0.015	BDL	0.013
		POM	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.003	0.002	0.017
		Monsoon	0.0168	0.0176	BDL	BDL	0.014	0.012	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.010
Iron	mgL ⁻¹	Winter	0.34	0.36	0.8	0.44	0.46	0.11	0.21	0.23	0.48	0.045
		Summer	0.425	0.45	1	0.55	0.575	0.137	0.262	0.287	0.6	0.056
		Monsoon	0.306	0.324	0.72	0.396	0.414	0.099	0.189	0.207	0.432	0.040
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.04	0.02	0.25	0.08	0.12	0.11	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.23
		POM	0.053	0.026	0.333	0.106	0.16	0.146	0.08	0.093	0.12	0.306
		Monsoon	0.032	0.016	0.2	0.064	0.096	0.088	0.048	0.056	0.072	0.184
Manganese	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.00	0.007	0.005	0.012	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.016
		POM	0.012	0.009	0.007	0.016	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.02
		Monsoon	0.010	0.007	0.006	0.014	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.017
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.016	BDL	0.02	0.019	BDL	BDL	0.020	BDL	0.002	0.001
		POM	0.021	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.003	0.002
		Monsoon	0.018	BDL	0.021	0.021	BDL	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.002	0.001
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.184	0.176	0.048	0.048	0.032	0.4
		POM	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.23	0.22	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.5
		Monsoon	0.043	0.043	0.043	0.043	0.201	0.192	0.052	0.052	0.035	0.437

Table 3. 8. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Amurhat (South Para) to Choudhuryhat Koutoli at different seasons.

Parameters	Units	Seasons										
			71. Amurhat (South para)	72. Amurhat (North para)	73. Amurhat (West para)	74. Fakirakhali (North)	75. Fakirakhali (middle para)	76. Fakirakhali(South para)	77. Boalkhali (Sourth)	78. Boalkhali (middle para)	79. Boalkhali (North)	80. Choudhuryhat Koutoli
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.01	0.01	0.01	BDL	BDL	0.01	0.02	0.01	BDL
		POM	BDL	0.02	0.01	0.02	BDL	BDL	0.02	0.03	0.01	BDL
		Monsoon	BDL	0.02	0.01	0.02	BDL	BDL	0.02	0.03	0.01	BDL
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.16	0.146	0.173	0.173	0.293	0.386	0.093	0.08	0.067	BDL
		POM	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.22	0.29	0.07	0.06	0.05	BDL
		Monsoon	0.108	0.099	0.117	0.117	0.198	0.261	0.063	0.054	0.045	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.0143	0.015	0.013	0.017	BDL	0.0176	BDL	BDL	0.013	BDL
		POM	0.013	0.014	0.012	0.016	BDL	0.016	BDL	BDL	0.012	BDL
		Monsoon	0.011	0.012	0.011	0.014	BDL	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.011	BDL
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.008	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.013	0.014	0.013	0.022	0.023	0.025
		POM	0.008	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.012	0.013	0.012	0.02	0.021	0.023
		Monsoon	0.007	0.007	0.005	0.004	0.010	0.011	0.01	0.017	0.018	0.020
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.056	BDL	0.051	BDL	BDL	0.052	0.053	0.052	BDL
		POM	BDL	0.07	BDL	0.063	BDL	BDL	0.065	0.066	0.065	BDL
		Monsoon	BDL	0.050	BDL	0.045	BDL	BDL	0.046	0.047	0.046	BDL
Iron	mgL ⁻¹	Winter	0.12	0.18	0.16	0.21	0.19	0.15	0.07	0.14	0.18	0.19
		Summer	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.11
		Monsoon	0.096	0.144	0.128	0.168	0.152	0.12	0.056	0.112	0.144	0.152
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.017	BDL	0.021	0.023	0.035	BDL	0.024
		POM	BDL	0.017	BDL	0.022	BDL	0.028	0.030	0.047	BDL	0.032
		Monsoon	BDL	0.010	BDL	0.013	BDL	0.016	0.018	0.028	BDL	0.019
Manganese	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.04	0.048	0.032	0.032	0.048	0.048	0.024	0.032	0.112	0.088
		POM	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.11
		Monsoon	0.043	0.052	0.035	0.035	0.052	0.052	0.026	0.035	0.122	0.096
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.028	0.025	0.018	0.077	0.04	0.024	0.002	0.006	0.002	0.005
		POM	0.035	0.032	0.023	0.097	0.05	0.03	0.003	0.008	0.003	0.006
		Monsoon	0.030	0.028	0.020	0.084	0.043	0.026	0.002	0.007	0.002	0.005
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.072	0.072	0.064	0.64	0.56	0.32	0.32	0.08	0.016	0.168
		POM	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.8	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.1	0.02	0.21
		Monsoon	0.078	0.078	0.07	0.7	0.612	0.35	0.35	0.087	0.017	0.183

Table 3. 9. Karnafuli River water resources quality from Koutoli (South)to Kumara Chor (North) at different seasons.

Parameters	Units	Seasons	81. koutoli	82. Kajibari	83. Kajibari	84.kalughat	85. Water	86. Soyabin	87. Soyabin	88. Kumirarchor(So	89. KumirarChor	90. KumirarChor(N
			(South)	(North)	(South)	(East)	supplier	factory	factory (South)	uth)		(South)
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.03	0.02	BDL	0.02	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.045	BDL	0.02
		POM	0.04	0.03	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.04	BDL	0.05	BDL	0.03
		Monsoon	0.04	0.03	BDL	0.03	BDL	0.04	BDL	0.05	BDL	0.03
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.04	0.05	0.36	0.346	0.36	0.12	0.106	0.12	0.08	0.066
		POM	0.03	0.04	0.27	0.26	0.27	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.05
		Monsoon	0.027	0.036	0.243	0.234	0.243	0.081	0.072	0.081	0.054	0.045
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.014	0.013	0.012	0.015	0.015	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.017	BDL
		POM	0.013	0.012	0.011	0.014	0.014	0.012	BDL	BDL	0.016	BDL
		Monsoon	0.011	0.0105	0.009	0.012	0.012	0.010	BDL	BDL	0.014	BDL
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.073	0.066	0.057	0.035	0.028	0.006	0.005	0.0233	0.222	0.02
		POM	0.066	0.06	0.052	0.032	0.026	0.006	0.005	0.021	0.2	0.018
		Monsoon	0.057	0.055	0.045	0.028	0.022	0.005	0.004	0.018	0.175	0.015
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.05	BDL	0.053	0.051	BDL	BDL	0.054	0.054	0.053
		POM	BDL	0.062	BDL	0.066	0.063	BDL	BDL	0.067	0.06	0.066
		Monsoon	BDL	0.045	BDL	0.047	0.045	BDL	BDL	0.048	0.048	0.047
Iron	mgL ⁻¹	Winter	0.51	0.48	0.81	0.75	0.65	0.16	0.17	0.582	0.45	0.09
		Summer	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.11
		Monsoon	0.408	0.384	0.648	0.6	0.52	0.128	0.136	0.465	0.36	0.072
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.017	0.015	BDL	0.025	0.024	BDL	BDL
		POM	BDL	0.024	BDL	0.022	0.02	BDL	0.033	0.032	BDL	BDL
		Monsoon	BDL	0.014	BDL	0.013	0.012	BDL	0.02	0.019	BDL	BDL
Manganese	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.12	0.024	0.024	0.032	0.032	0.096	0.088	0.024	0.037	0.032
		POM	0.15	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.12	0.11	0.03	0.047	0.04
		Monsoon	0.131	0.026	0.026	0.035	0.035	0.105	0.096	0.026	0.041	0.035
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.003	0.020	0.001	0.005	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.004
		POM	0.004	0.026	0.002	0.007	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.005
		Monsoon	0.003	0.022	0.001	0.006	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.004
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.032	0.032	0.024	0.024	0.064	0.064	0.032	0.032	0.018	0.017
		POM	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.023	0.022
		Monsoon	0.035	0.035	0.026	0.026	0.07	0.07	0.035	0.035	0.020	0.019

Table 3. 10. Karnaphuli River water resources quality from (Karnaphuli Paper Mill to Meshing hat) and (Air port to Navy gait) at different seasons.

Parameters	Units	Seasons										
			91. Karnaphuli Paper Mill	92. 250m South of Karnaphuli Paper Mill	93. Kola bagan	94. 400m South from Karnaphuli Paper Mill	95. 250m Karnaphuli Paper Mill from North	96. Meshinghat	97. Air port	98. Merine Academy	99. KAFCO	100. Navygait
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.018	BDL	0.018	0.02	0.01	BDL	0.009	0.01	BDL	0.01
		POM	0.02	BDL	0.02	0.03	0.01	BDL	0.01	0.01	BDL	0.02
		Monsoon	0.022	BDL	0.022	0.03	0.01	BDL	0.011	0.01	BDL	0.02
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	BDL	0.028	BDL	0.034	BDL	0.030	0.034	BDL	0.033	BDL
		POM	BDL	0.021	BDL	0.026	BDL	0.023	0.026	BDL	0.025	BDL
		Monsoon	BDL	0.018	BDL	0.023	BDL	0.020	0.023	BDL	0.022	BDL
Cobalt	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.013	0.014	BDL	BDL	0.012	BDL	0.015	0.013	0.016	0.015
		POM	0.012	0.013	BDL	BDL	0.011	BDL	0.014	0.012	0.015	0.014
		Monsoon	0.010	0.011	BDL	BDL	0.009	BDL	0.012	0.010	0.013	0.012
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.0577	0.057	0.05	0.062	0.067	0.068	0.068	0.057	0.056	0.057
		POM	0.052	0.05	0.053	0.056	0.061	0.062	0.062	0.052	0.051	0.052
		Monsoon	0.045	0.045	0.04	0.049	0.053	0.054	0.054	0.045	0.044	0.045
Copper	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.1	0.12	0.07	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.16	0.15	0.18	0.11
		POM	0.125	0.15	0.087	0.162	0.175	0.187	0.2	0.187	0.225	0.137
		Monsoon	0.09	0.108	0.063	0.117	0.126	0.135	0.144	0.135	0.162	0.099
Iron	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.51	0.48	0.81	0.75	0.65	0.16	0.17	0.58	0.45	0.09
		POM	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.11
		Monsoon	0.408	0.384	0.648	0.6	0.52	0.128	0.136	0.46	0.36	0.072
Lead	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.023	0.021	BDL	0.024	0.21	0.011	BDL	0.01	0.053	0.12
		POM	0.031	0.028	BDL	0.032	0.28	0.014	BDL	0.02	0.071	0.16
		Monsoon	0.018	0.016	BDL	0.019	0.168	0.008	BDL	0.012	0.042	0.096
Manganese	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.096	0.096	0.06	0.032	0.04	0.04	0.048	0.04	0.04	0.04
		POM	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05
		Monsoon	0.105	0.105	0.07	0.035	0.043	0.043	0.052	0.043	0.043	0.043
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.192	0.016	0.016	0.024	0.056	0.056	0.024	0.024	0.016	0.016
		POM	0.24	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02
		Monsoon	0.21	0.017	0.01	0.026	0.061	0.061	0.026	0.026	0.017	0.017
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	PRM	0.032	0.032	0.02	0.024	0.064	0.064	0.032	0.032	0.018	0.017
		POM	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.023	0.022
		Monsoon	0.035	0.035	0.02	0.026	0.07	0.07	0.035	0.035	0.020	0.019

Table 4. 1. Comparison study of Karnafuli River water resources quality (Sikolbaha Canal to Anumajhirghat) with inter country rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value WHO and BSTI.

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	0.02	0.009 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.004	0.025	0.0072 ± 0.001	0.003	0.0035	BDL	0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.012	0.13	0.0197 ± 0.003	0.015	0.012	0.013	Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.011	0.06	0.0228 ± 0.001	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.053	0.06	0.0331 ± 0.003	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.056	0.098	0.0817 ± 0.001	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.029	0.058	0.0406 ± 0.009	0.017	0.021	BDL	0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.4	2.03	1.1053 ± 0.053	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	0.025	0.02 ± 0.007	0.013	0.012	BDL	0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.04	0.0106 ± 0.001	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Table 4. 2. Comparison study of Karnafuli River water resources quality from Banglabaazar Ghat to Power point with inter country rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	0.03	0.014 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.004	0.024	0.006 ± 0.009	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.011	0.015	0.008 ± 0.007	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.052	0.058	0.033 ± 0.003	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.011	0.025	0.013 ± 0.002	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.01	0.26	0.196 ± 0.001	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.03	0.06	0.042 ± 0.001	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.07	0.62	0.183 ± 0.002	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.023	0.027	0.012 ± 0.003	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.015	0.007 ± 0.007	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Max= Maximum, Min= Minimum,

BSTI= Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institute and WHO= World Health Organization.

Table 4.3. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from under Karnafuli Bridge to JT No. 1. with inter country rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	0.03	0.02 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.003	0.021	0.007 ± 0.001	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.012	0.015	0.007 ± 0.0007	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.052	0.056	0.027 ± 0.002	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.011	0.016	0.0096 ± 0.001	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.22	0.38	0.275 ± 0.0053	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.07	0.0474 ± 0.002	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.2	0.0924 ± 0.001	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.021	0.024	0.0137 ± 0.002	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.013	0.018	0.0078 ± 0.001	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Table 4.4. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from JT No. 2 to JT No. 10. With inter country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.04	0.021 ± 0.01	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.008	0.023	0.008 ± 0.003	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.011	0.017	0.013 ± 0.001	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.051	0.061	0.033 ± 0.002	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.025	3.336 ± 0.085	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	1.63	4.84	0.013 ± 0.002	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.037	0.308	0.07 ± 0.0033	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.07	0.64	0.15 ± 0.0025	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.021	0.21	0.03 ± 0.0022	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.023	0.009 ± 0.001	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Max= Maximum, Min= Minimum,

BSTI= Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institute and WHO= World Health Organization.

Table 4. 5. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from Super Petrochemical to Dhanar Canal (North) with inter country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.05	0.021 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.0039	0.043	0.014 ± 0.001	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.012	0.13	0.018 ± 0.002	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.0266	0.055	0.026 ± 0.001	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.0065	0.018	0.006 ± 0.002	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	2.48	4.02	3.252 ± 0.005	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.038	0.05	0.041 ± 0.001	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.02	0.94	0.172 ± 0.001	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.022	0.24	0.04 ± 0.0015	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.021	0.025	0.016 ± 0.001	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Table 4. 6. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from Dhanar Canal to Aminpara with inter country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	0.03	0.013 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.015	0.18	0.05 ± 0.015	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.013	0.013	0.02 ± 0.003	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.011	0.016	0.001 ± 0.001	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.052	0.061	0.03 ± 0.001	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.124	3.84	2.679 ± 0.4	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.05	0.042 ± 0.001	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.1	0.074 ± 0.001	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.002	0.026	0.010 ± 0.003	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.012	0.26	0.134 ± 0.001	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Max= Maximum, Min= Minimum,

BSTI= Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institute and WHO= World Health Organization.

Table 4.7. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from Jelepura Canal to Choudhury Para with inters country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	0.02	0.011 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.12	0.75	0.401 ± 0.002	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.0074	0.018	0.012 ± 0.001	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.014	0.25	0.051 ± 0.003	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.03432	0.0652	0.144 ± 0.005	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.045	0.8	0.347 ± 0.004	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.013	0.022	0.011 ± 0.001	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.02	0.25	0.11 ± 0.002	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.003	0.02	0.008 ± 0.001	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.04	0.5	0.131 ± 0.003	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Table 4. 8. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from Amurhat (South Para) to Choudhuryhat Koutoli with inter country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	0.03	0.022 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.05	0.29	0.118 ± 0.085	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.012	0.016	0.0083 ± 0.001	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.0008	0.023	0.0264 ± 0.002	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.051	0.056	0.0121 ± 0.003	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.07	0.21	0.159 ± 0.04	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.013	0.035	0.0133 ± 0.001	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.03	0.14	0.063 ± 0.0034	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.003	0.097	0.0287 ± 0.002	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	0.08	0.285 ± 0.028	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Max= Maximum, Min= Minimum,

BSTI= Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institute and WHO= World Health Organization.

Table 4. 9. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from Koutoli (South) to Kumara Char (North) with inter country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.05	0.023 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.03	0.27	0.124 ± 0.002	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.051	0.059	0.027 ± 0.001	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.011	0.016	0.009 ± 0.001	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.005	0.026	0.107 ± 0.004	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.09	0.81	0.465 ± 0.005	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.015	0.025	0.01 ± 0.001	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.03	0.15	0.064 ± 0.003	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.002	0.026	0.006 ± 0.001	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.022	0.08	0.042 ± 0.01	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Table 4. 10. Comparison study with Karnafuli River water resources quality from Karnafuli Paper Mill to Meshing hat, Airport to Navy gait with inter country Rivers (Halda, Meghna and Sango) and standard value (WHO and BSTI).

Parameters	Units	Min	Max	Mean	Halda	Sango	Meghna	WHO	BSTI
Arsenic	mgL ⁻¹	0.01	0.03	0.017 ± 0.001	0.04	0.01		0.01	0.05
Cadmium	mgL ⁻¹	0.021	0.026	0.0121 ± 0.001	0.003	0.0035		0.005	0.003
Cobalt	mg L ⁻¹	0.051	0.062	0.0553 ± 0.004	0.015	0.012		Max. 0.1	Max. 0.1
Copper	mg L ⁻¹	0.003	0.11	0.0091 ± 0.001	0.01	0.013	0.024	0.3-1.0	0.1-1.0
Chromium	mgL ⁻¹	0.011	0.015	0.0278 ± 0.003	0.051	0.053	0.013	0.05	0.05
Iron	mg L ⁻¹	0.07	0.18	0.131 ± 0.03	0.043	0.055	0.59	1.0	1.0
Lead	mg L ⁻¹	0.011	0.21	0.0477 ± 0.006	0.017	0.021		0.01	0.05
Manganese	mg L ⁻¹	0.04	0.12	0.067 ± 0.02	0.08	0.07	0.08	Max. 0.1	0.5
Nickel	mgL ⁻¹	0.001	0.021	0.005 ± 0.0012	0.013	0.012		0.07	0.02
Zinc	mgL ⁻¹	0.02	0.24	0.055 ± 0.006	0.011	0.01	0.039	5	3.0

Max= Maximum, Min= Minimum,
 BSTI= Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institute and WHO= World Health Organization.

Fig. 5. 1. Showing the Arsenic values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5. 2. Showing the Cadmium values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5. 3. Showing the Cobalt values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5. 4. Showing the Copper values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5.5. Showing the Chromium values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5.6. Showing the Iron values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5. 7. Showing the Lead values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10))

Fig. 5. 8. Showing the Manganese values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5.9. Showing the Nickel values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Fig. 5.10. Showing the Zinc values of Karnafuli River water quality (Table no. (4.1–4.10)).

Table 6.1. Pearson Correlations among the different parameters of Karnafuli River.

	As	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Pb	Mn	Nickel	Zinc
As	1	-.178	.148	-.119	-.181	.431(**)	.057	-.028	-.039	-.034
Cd	-.178	1	.379(*)	-.179	.466(**)	-.254(*)	-.465(**)	-.081	-.143	.164
Co	.148	.379(*)	1	-.139	-.092	.170	-.082	-.042	-.087	.225
Cr	-.119	-.179	-.139	1	-.101	-.133	.194	-.015	-.090	.262
Cu	-.181	.466(**)	-.092	-.101	1	-.181	-.301(*)	-.069	-.339(**)	.016
Fe	.431(**)	-.254(*)	.170	-.133	-.181	1	.191	-.058	.045	-.035
Pb	.057	-.465(**)	-.082	.194	-.301(*)	.191	1	-.062	.074	-.186
Mn	-.028	-.081	-.042	-.015	-.069	-.058	-.062	1	.001	-.190
Ni	-.039	-.143	-.087	-.090	-.339(**)	.045	.074	.001	1	-.169
Zn	-.034	.164	.225	.262	.016	-.035	-.186	-.190	-.169	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

Arsenic

Arsenic of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10))that all the samples have arsenic values around 0.05-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.05-mgL⁻¹) was found at Super Petrochemical point and the lowest value (BDL) was found at high and low tide in winter season at many points. Arsenic was found positively correlation with Co, Fe and Pb.

Cadmium

Cadmium of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10))that all the samples have cadmium values around 0.03-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.75-mgL⁻¹) was found at Jeleparakhal point and the lowest value (BDL) was found at high and low tide in winter season at Sadarghat points. Iron was found positively correlation with As, Ni and Pb.

Cobalt

Cobalt of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10))that all the samples have cobalt values around 0.03-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.06-mgL⁻¹) was found at Kumara char point and the lowest value (BDL) was found at high and low tide in winter season at many points. Cobalt was found positively correlation with As, Ni and Pb.

Chromium

Chromium of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10))that all the samples have chromium values around 0.05-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.06-mgL⁻¹) was found at Raja Khali canal point and the lowest value (BDL) was

found at high and low tide in winter season at many points. Chromium was found positively correlation with Pb and Zinc.

Copper

Copper of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10)) that all the samples have copper values around BDL-4.00-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (3.84-mgL⁻¹) was found at JT No.6 point and the lowest value (BDL) was found at high and low tide in winter season at Sadarghat points. Iron was found positively correlation with As, Ni and Pb.

Iron

Iron of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10)) that all the samples have iron values around BDL-4.00-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (3.84-mgL⁻¹) was found at JT No.6 point and the lowest value (BDL) was found at high and low tide in winter season at Sadarghat points. Iron was found positively correlation with As, Ni and Pb.

Lead

Lead of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10)) that all the samples have lead values around 0.05-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.07-mgL⁻¹) was found at under Karnafuli bridge point. Lead was found negatively correlation with Co, Cu, Mn and Zn.

Manganese

Manganese is a vital micro-nutrient for both plants and animals. Inadequate quantities of manganese in domestic animal food results in reduced reproductive capabilities and deformed or poorly maturing young [25]. Manganese of the Karnafuli River water shows Table (1-10) that most of the samples were found below 0.80-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (2.03-mgL⁻¹) was found at low tide in summer and winter seasons at Jalilgang canal point and lowest value (0.02-mgL⁻¹) was found also at high and low tides in summer season at Star cement (east) points. Manganese was found negatively correlated with As, Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Pb, Ni and Zn.

Nickel

Nickel of the Karnafuli River water shows ((Table (1-10))) that all the samples have nickel values around 0.04-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.047-mgL⁻¹) was found at Kirakhali (North) point. Iron was found negatively correlation with Mn, Pb and Fe.

Zinc

Zinc of the Karnafuli River water shows (Table (1-10)) that all the samples have zinc values around 0.06-mgL⁻¹. Highest value (0.8-mgL⁻¹) was found at Fakirakhali (North) point and the lowest value (BDL) was found at high and low tide in winter season at Sadarghat points. Iron was found positively correlation Cd, Co and Cr.

Conclusions

The main sources of pollutants generating both from inorganic and organic wastes were found to originate from industrial and agricultural activities, unsustainable development and household activities of local people. These waste materials were ultimately contaminating the Karnafuli River water. Due to this spawning of carps are decreasing gradually and lesser quantities of fish eggs are being harvested nowadays. Peoples are suffering from different types of water born diseases of these areas. Peoples of the holly regions are using acidic water continuous consumption may cause gastric and ulcer to them. The summary of the Karnafuli River water quality is presented in **(Table (1-10))**. It clearly indicates that this river water is not suitable for domestic purpose use. Metal namely Cadmium, Cobalt, Copper, Chromium, Iron, Lead, Manganese, Nickel, Zinc in most of the sports were present in trace amount. These complied with permissible limit. But Fe, Zn, Pb, Mn in most of the sports were found to be higher than that of standard values recommended by BSTI. Comparison of water quality of the Halda, Karnafuli and Sango **Table (4.1-4.10)** shows that Karnafuli is most polluted among the rivers of this region. The urban runoff and industrial waste water discharged in the Karnafuli were the major threat of the river water quality at Chittagong. Like other city belt rivers the Karnafuli is losing its water quality day by day. From our toxic metal analyses we saw that some of the water quality parameters have existed within the tolerance limits. Still it is the prime to control the pollution of Karnafuli River before it had been turned into a dead river.

So it is very much necessary for more research on this river and increase people awareness about the effect and remedies of pollution. Result from this study show that Karnafuli River water of greater Chittagong district is toxic in nature. This affects not only the aquatic environmental and human beings of the surroundings but also poses a serious threat to Karnafuli River water resources of the adjoining areas. For this reason from the agriculture fields, irrigated by these polluted rivers' water of Chittagong region. It is possible that wastewater may have entered in food chain.

- (This study has direct impact on economy of our country, human health and standards for our drinking water, agricultural, industrial and livestock requirements.)
- (In order to create public awareness about the freshwater pollution due to the discharge of untreated industrial waste, this article will be published in national magazines, newspapers and international journal.)

From present study it is found that the Karnafuli River water becomes polluted from industries, municipal and agricultural sources. Industrial and municipal effluents must be discharge into river after proper treatment. Many industries have effluent treatment plants, but they are not using it. Only tidal cycle is keeping river alive. If there were no tidal cycle, the Karnafuli would have been turned into a dead river like as Buriganga and Turag of Dhaka. So the Chittagong municipal authority should take a lead role in organizing a concrete and concerted

effort with other government and non government agencies in solving the problems of the Karnafuli River as soon as possible. Step must be taken to save the Halda River from getting polluted by the Karnafuli River water especially in the pre-monsoon season when flow of this river decreases.

Recommendations

To obtain acceptable effluent from the river water, the following recommendation is to be taken into consideration

- ✓ (Besides the Karnafuli River, industry should be established ETP (effluent treatment plant) in their own factory.
- ✓ ETP must be established in each and every industry.
- ✓ All kinds of obstruction must be removed from the way of river flow.
- ✓ Use of highly toxic pesticides must be avoided.
- ✓ Awareness must be increased among the people who live in the bank of river.
- ✓ Proper steps should be taken by CCC, CWASA, CDA and River commission.
- ✓ The dumping system should be modified.
- ✓ To acquire and the upcoming sustainable development goals, river must be free from all form of pollutions and hazards.)

Above all, the Government should make new legislation on saving the Karnafuli River and it should also take step to apply the laws, because the polluted water not only affects the river, but also endangers the beings living on it and also effect navigation of the Chittagong Port. Therefore to prevent future adverse impact on the river a restriction must be imposed on the discharge of trace metals and sewages through different sources.

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References

- [1]. M. J. Ahmed, M. R. Haque, A. Ahsan, S. Siraj, M. H. R. Bhuiyan, S. C. Bhattacharjee and S. Islam, (2010) “Physicochemical Assessment of Surface and Groundwater Quality of the Greater Chittagong Region of Bangladesh” *Pak. J. Anal. Environ. Chem.*, 11(2),1-11.
- [2]. T. Jayaseelan, R. Damodaran, P. Mani, (2015) “Analysis of Physicochemical Properties of Waste Water Effluents from Textile Industries Area of Tipura, Tamil Nadu, India”, *Acta Biomedica Scientia*, 2(2), 84-89.
- [3]. J. Karthikeyan, S.V. Mohon, (1999) “Advances in Industrial Pollution Control”, 1st ed, *Techno. Science Publications*, pp. 250 262.
- [4].J. A. Awomeso, A. M. Taiwo, A. M. Gbadebo and J. A. Adenowo, (2010) “Studies on The Pollution of Waterbody by Textile Industry Effluents in Lagos, Nigeria”, *Journal of Applied Sciences in Environmental Sanitation*, 5 (4), 353-365
- [5]. J. U. Harun, (2006) “Chittagong District”, *Banglapedia: National Encyclopedia of Bangladesh*, Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh, (http://www.banglapedia.org/http_do_cs/HT_/C_0212.HTM)
- [6].S. Murphy, (2007) “BASIN Water Quality Terminology”, *Boulder Area Sustainability Network*,URL: <http://bc.n.boulder.co.us/basin/natural/wqterms.html> (last accessed on 20th June, 2011)
- [7].B. K. Sharma (2003) “Environmental Chemistry”, 7th ed, *GOEL Publishing House, Meerut*. Unit-3, pp. 259 - 379
- [8]. A. Mojiri, (2011) “Effects of Municipal Wastewater on Physical and Chemical Properties of Saline Soil”, *J. Biol. Environ. Sci.*,5 (14),71 - 78
- [9].B. K. Sharma, (2000) “Environmental Chemistry”, 7th ed., *GOEL Publishing House, Meerut*, Unit-4, pp.390 – 415
- [10]. Anonymous, (2011) “Specific Conductivity”, URL: http://www.ourlake.org/html/specific_conductivity.html. (Last accessed on 20th June, (2011)
- [11]. “Water quality parameters in river management monitoring project, Kentucky water watch”, (1994), URL: <http://kywater.org/www-/ramp/rmtss.htm>. (last accessed on 17th July, 2011)
- [12]. J. Rhoades, “Information on Chloride and Plant Growth”, (2011), URL: <http://www.gardeningknowhow.com/gardeninghow-to/information-on-chloride-and-plant-growth.htm>, (last accessed on 22nd July, 2011)
- [13]. O, Faroon, A. Ashizawa,S. Wright, (2012) “Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry”,US.

- [14]. Kallol Dey, S. C. Mohapatra and M. Biduabarimisra (2005) “Assessment of water quality parameters of the river of water Brahmani at Rourkela”, *Journal of Industrial Pollution Control*, 21(2), 299-304
- [15]. Umunnakwe John Bosco, E. A. O. Nnaji and P. I. Ejimmaduekwu, (2011), “Preliminary assessment of some physicochemical parameters during dredging of Nworie River, Owerri”, *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 10 (3), 269-273.
- [16]. Pradip K. Maurya, D S. Malik, (2016) “Distribution of heavy metals in water, sediments and fish tissue (*Heteropneustis fossilis*) in Kali River of western U.P. India”, *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies*; 4(2), 208-215
- [17]. HazratAli, Ezzat Khan and Ikram Ilahi, (2019) “Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology of Hazardous Heavy Metals: Environmental Persistence, Toxicity, and Bioaccumulation” , *Journal of Chemistry*, 7(2), 235 -246
- [18]. Kari-Matti Vuori, (1995) “Direct and indirect effects of iron on river ecosystems” *Annales Zoologici Fennici, Aquatic ecotoxicology-study of freshwater systems stressed by toxic chemical* , Vol. 32, No. 3, pp. 317-329
- [19]. K. Arun, T. Shanker, C. Cervantes, H. Loza-Tavera, and S. Avudainayagam, (2005), “Chromium Toxicity in Plants”, *Environment International*, 31,739 - 751
- [20]. R. Eisler, (1986) “Chromium Hazards to Fish, Wildlife, and Invertebrates: A Synoptic Review”, *Biological Report*, Patuxent Wildlife Research Center, U.S.A, pp.5-12
- [21]. B. K. Sharma, “Environmental Chemistry”, (2000), 7th ed., *GOEL Publishing House*, Meerut, Unit-4, pp.376 – 389.
- [22]. R. Eisler, (1993), “Zinc Hazards to Fish, Wildlife, and Invertebrates: A Synoptic Review”, *Biological Report*, Patuxent Wildlife Research Center, U.S.A, pp. 106 – 115
- [23]. Hisham NaifWafi (2015) “Assessment of Heavy Metals Contamination in the Mediterranean Sea along Gaza Coast – A case Study of Gaza Fishing Harbor”, *A Thesis of Master of Water and Environmental Science*, Institute of Water and Environment, Al-Azhar University-Gaza, 2015.
- [24]. Umair Ashraf, Adam ShekaKanu, Zhaowen Mo Saddam Hussain, Shakeel Ahmad Anjum, Imran Khan, Rana Nadeem Abbas and Xiangru Tang, (2015) “Lead toxicity in rice: effects, mechanisms, and mitigation strategies—a mini review”, *Environ Sci. Pollution Res.*, 8(3), 233 - 242
- [25]. PeterCadmus, Stephen F. Brinkman, and Melynda K.May.,(2018) “Chronic Toxicity of Ferric Iron for North American Aquatic Organisms: Derivation of a Chronic Water Quality Criterion Using Single Species and Mesocosm Data”, *Arch Environ Contamn.Toxicol*;74(4), 605–615.
- [26]. B. Chiswell and D. Huang, (2006) in “Interface Science and Technology”, <http://www.lenntech.com/periodic/elements/p.htm>, (last accessed on 26th July, 2011).

- [27]. L. S. Clesceri, A. E. Greenberg, and A. D. Eaton, (1999) “Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater”, *American Public Health Association*, 20th edn, Washington, D.C.
- [28]. DIN, Deutsche Industrial Norms, Recommended Methods, “Water and Environmental Analysis with the UV/VIS Spectrophotometer Lambda 2”, Hubertheim, Hanswilly Muller, Inge Witte *Bodenseewerk Perkin -Elmer GmbH, D-7770, Uberlingen, Germany.*
- [29]. J. Basselt, R. C. Denny, G. H. Jeffery and J. Mendham, (1989) “Vogel’s textbook of quantity inorganic analysis”, 5th edn, *ELBS, John Wiley Sons Inc.* pp. 730 - 745
- [30]. L. S. Clesceri, A. E. Greenberg, and A. D. Eaton, (1999). “Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater”, *American Public Health Association*, 20th edn, Washington, D. C, pp. 303 – 325.
- [31]. S. Dey, J. Das and M. A. Manchur, (2015), “ Studies on Heavy Metal Pollution of Karnafuli River, Chittagong, Bangladesh”, *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 9(8), 79 – 83.
- [32]. H. Rashid, M. N. Hasan, M. B. Tanu , R. Parveen, Z. P. Sukhan, M. S. Rahman,. and Y. Mahmud, (2012) “Heavy Metal Pollution and Chemical Profile of Khiru River, Bangladesh”., *International Journal of Environment*, 2(1), 57–63.

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